

Bioactives from microalgal dinoflagellates

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Abstract

Dinoflagellate microalgae are an important source of marine biotoxins. Bioactives from dinoflagellates are attracting increasing attention because of their impact on the safety of seafood and potential uses in biomedical, toxicological and pharmacological research. Here we review the potential applications of dinoflagellate toxins and the methods for producing them. Only sparing quantities of dinoflagellate toxins are generally available and this hinders bioactivity characterization and evaluation in possible applications. Approaches to production of increased quantities of dinoflagellate bioactives are discussed. Although many dinoflagellates are fragile and grow slowly, controlled culture in bioreactors appears to be generally suitable for producing many of the metabolites of interest.

Keywords: Dinoflagellates, microalgae, marine toxins, shear-sensitivity, photobioreactor

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1. Introduction

This review is focused on the potential medical and commercial significance of dinoflagellate bioactives. Possible methods for producing quantities of the toxins for evaluation in various applications, are discussed. Bioactives of nondinoflagellate phytoplanktons have been reviewed elsewhere (Shimizu, 2003; Singh et al., 2005).

More than 21,000 structurally diverse bioactive natural products have been isolated from marine species since the 1970s (Blunt et al., 2009). Dinoflagellates are a major source these compounds. Some of the bioactives initially isolated from the other marine invertebrates have been shown to actually originate from dinoflagellates (Dunlap et al., 2007). Most of these molecules have not progressed beyond the discovery stage because of limited availability from the natural source and difficulty of synthesis due to structural complexity. Many source species, especially dinoflagellates, invertebrates and/or their symbionts, have proven difficult to culture in the laboratory, or have failed to produce the desired compound under the artificial culture conditions (Faulkner, 2000; Haefner, 2003). Notwithstanding the difficulties, a number of marine bioactivities have been the focus of developmental effort for producing therapeutically useful substances. Several marine bioactives are in clinical or preclinical testing for possible treatment of cancer, inflammation and other ailments (Glaser, 2009). Of the compounds under clinical evaluation, none has been sourced from dinoflagellates, despite their being the major source of marine bioactives.

The Division Dinoflagellata consists of an estimated 2,000 living species. Only about half the dinoflagellates photosynthesize; the rest of the species are symbiotic or parasitic, living in association with marine animals (Taylor, 1987; Taylor, 2003). Dinoflagellates are most commonly associated with harmful algal blooms (HABs) that occur from time to time. Although most algal blooms are harmless, nearly 70 algal species are known to be toxic. Marine algal toxins have been traditionally classified on the basis of their effects on humans: azaspiracid

poisoning (AZP), amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP), ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP), diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP), neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP) and paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) are generally known (Hallegraeff, 2003). Most instances of poisoning go unreported. Consequently, the real global impact of toxin-induced disease is difficult to estimate. In addition to the toxins commonly associated with health effects, dinoflagellates produce some of the largest and most complex polyketides and other secondary metabolites that have been identified (Shimizu, 2003; Kobayashi et al., 2003; Kobayashi and Kubota, 2007; Rein and Snyder, 2006; Hu et al., 2010; Kellmann et al., 2010). Novel dinoflagellate toxins continue to be found (Holland et al., 2012).

2. Applications of dinoflagellate bioactives

2.1 Assessment of seafood safety

Safety of fish and other seafood depends on the extent of its contamination with dinoflagellate toxins. Consequently, samples must be regularly analyzed for the levels of biotoxins present. Validation and calibration of toxin assays requires reference standards of toxins. Reference materials are necessary also for establishing the identity of unknown samples of toxins. An increasing number of certified reference standards of marine biotoxins is available from the National Research Council of Canada's Certified Reference Materials Program (www.imb.nrc.ca/crmp/), but the supply tends to be limited and products are sometimes unavailable. In principle, reference standards could be produced by chemical synthesis, but synthesis of most dinoflagellate toxins is complicated, if at all feasible.

Only a few marine biotoxins are available commercially (Quilliam, 2003). Small quantities of a few dinoflagellate biotoxins are commercially available from the sources noted in Table 1. A given product can vary a great deal in price, depending on the source and the claimed purity. Some products are available only from a single supplier. The problem of

inexpensively obtaining quantities of toxins for various investigational purposes persists. Prices range from a few hundred Euros per mg to more than €30,000 per mg (Table 1). The commercially available biotoxins (Table 1) are derived from an extremely small number of dinoflagellate species: *Prorocentrum concavum*, *Ptychodiscus brevis* (*Gymnodinium breve*), *Gambierdiscus toxicus* and *Protogonyalax* sp. In many cases, the credibility of the stated quantity and purity are questionable (Quilliam, 2003). Most of the poorly authenticated commercial products are not suitable for use as reference standards (Quilliam, 2003).

The most widely accepted method for detection and quantification of many marine toxins in suspect samples remains the mouse bioassay. This method requires intraperitoneally injecting mice with extracts of toxic seafood. For safety testing of oysters, for example, three mice are injected with an extract of the digestive glands of oysters. If two or more mice die within 24 h of injection, the shellfish are considered unsafe to eat. After extensive evaluations against the mouse bioassay, other physicochemical testing procedures not requiring the use of animals, have become the standard in the European Union (EU) for certain toxicity tests. The EU no longer requires the mouse bioassay for testing the safety of shellfish. For certain marine toxins, high performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection (HPLC-FLD) and liquid chromatography in tandem with mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) are accepted for establishing the safety of seafood. In the event of a discrepancy between the results of a newer test method and the mouse bioassay, the latter retains validity. Other methods are being established to replace the mouse bioassay.

Antibody-based immunoassays are potentially useful for accurate, sensitive and routine determinations of marine toxins (Wong et al., 2010). Attempts are being made to reduce the expense of these assays and increase their portability. An antibody-based assay typically takes the form of an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) or a radioimmunoassay (RIA). Unfortunately, because of a lack of a supply of highly pure toxins,

relatively few antibody-based assays are available and batch-to-batch variations of a given assay can be high. In addition, the cross-reactivity of antibodies with non-target molecules poses a problem as most toxin-producing dinoflagellates produce various analogs of a given toxin, or multiple similar toxins. Portable immunodetection methods that are useful for establishing contamination with toxins involved in paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP), diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP), neurotoxic shellfish poisoning (NSP), and ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) have been reviewed elsewhere (Garcia Camacho et al., 2007a). An ELISA for the determination of okadaic acid in shellfish has been reported (Wang et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2012). Other physicochemical procedures such as LC-MS and HPLC have been developed for detection and quantification of many toxins (Pierce and Kirkpatrick, 2001; Quilliam, 2003; Samdal et al., 2005; Humpage et al., 2010).

2.2 Detection and identification of HAB species

Bioactive compounds produced by an alga and the genetic machinery responsible for the production can become the basis for identifying and monitoring harmful algae. Detection and monitoring of harmful algal blooms (HAB) are potentially useful for management of fisheries, seafood safety and tourism (Anderson, 2009). Consumer protection through an improved knowledge of the dynamics of HAB can lead to substantial savings in unwanted expenses (Scatasta et al., 2003).

In view of their slow growth rates, the ability of dinoflagellates to cyclically provoke blooms with thousands of cells per milliliter in only a few days (Hallegraeff, 2003), may be surprising. This rapid increase in cell concentration in local coastal areas appears to be related more to oceanic flow patterns and winds that concentrate biomass in areas of low turbulence, and less to any sudden change in the growth rate of the cells. HAB detection and monitoring programs of particular note are the Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal

Blooms (GEOHAB; www.geohab.info/) program and the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's NOAA Harmful Algal Bloom Operational Forecast System (<http://tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/hab/>).

HAB detection and monitoring have classically relied on sampling and taxonomic identification. Automated image analysis of algal cells is an emerging technology that can potentially assist in rapid morphology-based identification of HAB species. Microscopy and pigment analysis can be combined in a single device, as in the benchtop FlowCAM[®] (www.fluidimaging.com). This flow cytometric device captures a microscopic image and measures fluorescence from chlorophyll and phycoerythrin. Increasingly, airborne and satellite-based optical remote sensing are being used for monitoring HABs. For example, *Karenia brevis* blooms have been monitored using satellite-based observations of chlorophyll levels (Tester et al., 2008). Optical remote sensing is useful mainly for surface monitoring and fails to detect any sub-surface blooms. In addition, remote sensing does not distinguish between toxic blooms and blooms of nontoxic species.

Remote optical detection of blooms has traditionally been possible only at relatively high concentrations of the bloom-causing species. Commercial optical sensing instruments include fluorometers, transmissometers and turbidimeters (Moore et al., 2008; Moore et al., 2009) deployed on various types of fixed and mobile robotic platforms. An advanced optical plankton discriminator (OPD, the "Brevebuster") has been successfully employed for monitoring blooms of *K. brevis* (Sellner et al., 2003). Despite advances in technology, optical remote monitoring is not possible for a majority of the harmful algal species. Other problems associated with optical monitoring and forecasting have been discussed (Schofield et al., 1999).

Use of highly-specific molecular tools in identifying harmful dinoflagellates is highly promising (Tyrrell et al., 1997; Adachi et al., 1996; Bowers et al., 2000; Rublee et al., 2001;

Litaker and Tester, 2002; Rublee et al., 2005; Kudela et al., 2010; Galluzzi et al., 2011). Strategies for molecular detection and characterization of HAB species have been reviewed (Rublee et al., 2001; Litaker and Tester, 2002; Rublee et al., 2005). Molecular methods include conventional PCR, real-time PCR, denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE), fluorescent fragment detection PCR, fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH), and lectins, antibodies and ribosomal RNA (rRNA)-targeted DNA probes. A system for simultaneous detection of multiple species has been developed (Scorzetti, 2009). Use of 14 species-specific probes and 4 sets of specific primers allows for a theoretical identification of up to 100 different species in a single sample.

Highly specific monoclonal antibodies (MAbs) may be potentially used for species identification (Adachi, 1993; Gas, 2009), but only a few MAbs that specifically bind peptides, glycoproteins, and toxins are available commercially for HAB species (Anderson, 1995; Scholin and Anderson, 1998; Peperzak et al., 2000; Cho and Costas, 2004; Garcia Camacho et al., 2007a). Polyclonal antibodies are not generally satisfactory as they commonly cross-react with multiple HAB species (Mendoza et al., 1995). Identification based on MAbs has been quite successful in some cases (Adachi, 1993; Gas, 2009).

2.3 New products

Although many compounds isolated from dinoflagellates have shown bioactivities of interest (Blunt et al., 2009; Garcia Camacho et al., 2007a), only a few have led to commercial products. This is partly because of a limited supply of dinotoxins makes their detailed clinical evaluation impossible. An example of a drug being developed from a dinoflagellate toxin is TetrodinTM. This product is derived from tetrodotoxin (TTX), a potent neurotoxin. TetrodinTM is being developed by WEX Pharmaceuticals Inc. (www.wexpharma.com) for use in cancer-related pain management (Hagen et al., 2007; Hagen et al., 2008). TetrodinTM is made from

TTX sourced from pufferfish, as TTX production from dinoflagellates has not been developed.

Okadaic acid is another example of a marine biotoxin that has proven useful in medical research (Fernández et al., 2002). Because of its activity as an inhibitor of protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A), okadaic acid is used regularly in studies where inhibition of PP2A is wanted (Redden and Dodge-Kafka, 2011; Morita et al., 2011). Tumor promoting and cytotoxic activities of okadaic acid are of potential interest (Islam et al., 2002; Kim et al., 2009).

Several recent patents and patent applications relating to dinoflagellate toxins have been published (Murakami et al., 2006; Wong et al., 2008; Selander and Pavia, 2009; Paul, 2011; Neilan et al., 2011). These most commonly discuss methods for detection of a toxin or a HAB species. Methods for culturing the producing species and recovery/purification of toxins are also discussed. Only rarely does a patent relate to application of a new product in medicine or industry.

2.4 Immunology studies

A variety of animal and human cell types have been used to study the effects of dinoflagellates bioactives (Wang, 2008). Such studies are useful in identifying possible mechanisms of bioactivity and development of potential pharmacological agents. To be extrapolated to animal models *in vivo*, an *in vitro* study with cells needs to use the kinds of concentrations of the bioactive that would occur in bloodstream or tissue after ingestion of contaminated seafood. In addition to studies of the effects of bioactives on cells *in vitro*, immunological studies in animal models are also necessary, for example, in attempts to develop antidotes and vaccines that protect against toxins.

Commercial vaccines against poisonings by dinoflagellate toxins do not exist currently, but promising attempts have been made to produce suitable vaccines. For example, Xu et al. (2005a; 2005b) succeeded in protecting mice against otherwise lethal doses of tetrodotoxin (TTX) using a vaccine that elicited production of TTX-neutralizing antibodies. Although some marine algal toxins are known to affect the immune system (Ito et al., 2000; Ito et al., 2002; Franchinia et al., 2005), little is known about their immunoregulatory potential. Some of marine toxins are able to alter the phosphorylation state of cellular proteins leading to a collapse of the normal regulatory processes and other molecular alterations (Fernández et al., 2002). For example, yessotoxin (YTX) and okadaic acid regulate protein kinase C (PKC) and phosphatase 2A (PP2A) activities. In lymphocytes, the expression level of the T cell receptor (TCR) and the T cell responsiveness are regulated by a balance between PKC and PP2A activities that can be influenced by certain toxins. Martin López et al. (2011) using mouse T-lymphocyte EL-4 demonstrated that both YTX and okadaic acid through different mechanisms induced a down-regulation of TCR expression, compromising T cell activation.

3. Production of toxins and bioactives

Around 150 g of a pure bioactive is typically needed for preclinical studies and clinical trials required for gaining approval of the regulatory bodies for use of the bioactive as a drug. Production of 150 g of a dinoflagellate bioactive is estimated to require a culture broth volume of 10^3 to 10^5 m³ (Shimizu, 2000). This is much too large compared to the volume of the fermentation broth needed to produce the same quantity of a typical antibiotic such as penicillin G. The handling of such a large volume of a highly toxic dinoflagellate broth could be a major hurdle. The broth handling task can be greatly simplified by raising the concentration of the bioactive in the broth. An elevated concentration of the bioactive will

also reduce its cost of production (Chisti, 2007). Enhancements in concentration of a target compound are likely to be made by improving the producer strain through selection and genetic modification, as previously demonstrated for many commercial antibiotics derived from fungi and bacteria. An improved technology of production will further contribute to making large-scale production affordable. Advances that have the potential to impact the production of the bioactives are already being made as discussed in Sections 3.2 and 3.3.

3.1 Chemical synthesis

In principle, dinoflagellates toxins and reference standards could be produced by chemical synthesis, but de novo synthesis of most toxins is difficult, if at all feasible. Where a total synthesis has been accomplished, it has typically required more than 100 steps. Development of more practical synthetic routes remains a challenge (Suzuki et al., 2005). Commercially, only okadaic acid appears to have been produced via chemical synthesis by Sigma-Aldrich (www.sigmaaldrich.com) and VWR International (www.vwrsp.com), but the synthetic product is apparently no longer available. Nevertheless, chemical synthesis has significantly contributed to elucidation of the structures of several complex bioactives of dinoflagellates (Nicolaou et al., 2004a; Nicolaou et al., 2004b; Hirama, 2005).

Syntheses have been demonstrated for several bioactives, including hemibrevetoxin B (Nicolaou et al., 1993), brevetoxin B (Nicolaou et al., 1995), brevetoxin A (Nicolaou et al., 1999), ciguatoxin CTX3C (Hirama, 2005), gymnocin-A (Tsukano et al., 2005), gambierol (Majumder et al., 2006) and amphidinolide V (Fürstner et al., 2009). In addition, characteristic fragments of toxins (typically polycyclic ether ring systems) have been produced and more efficient synthetic routes have been proposed for some compounds (Nakata, 2005; Nicholas and Phillips, 2006; Oishi et al., 2006; Crimmins et al., 2006; Fuwa and Sasaki, 2007; Morita et al., 2008a; Morita et al., 2008b; Satoh et al., 2008).

Small quantities of synthetically produced pure equivalents of a bioactive can be particularly useful in producing monoclonal antibodies for its unambiguous detection (Hirama, 2005). An unambiguous understanding of the structure of a toxin can be used in synthesizing its antagonists that may be used as antidotes. For example, β -naphthoyl-brevetoxin, a semisynthetic brevetoxin antagonist and its derivative, are being used in investigating the mechanisms of bronchoconstriction induced by inhaled brevetoxins and in reversing the effect of the toxin (Michelliza et al., 2007).

3.2 Genetic improvements

Potentially increased titers of a bioactive may be obtained by using a production strain that has been genetically modified for improved productivity. Genetic and metabolic engineering of dinoflagellates is not straightforward. Dinoflagellate genome is unusual compared to the other eukaryote genomes (Moreno Díaz de la Espina et al., 2005; Jaeckisch et al., 2011). The nuclear genomes of most dinoflagellate species are extraordinarily large (Wisecaver and Hackett, 2011) and organized into a permanently condensed liquid-crystalline state. Sequencing a large genome is complicated. Nevertheless, large-scale expressed sequence tag programs have been initiated for several species (Hackett, 2004; Bachvaroff, 2004; Hackett et al., 2005).

The dinoflagellate genome has a high proportion of unusual bases that limit the usefulness of many cloning enzymes (Rein and Borrone, 1999). Furthermore, the genome is replete with introns (Kubota et al., 2006) and redundant repetitive non-coding sequences (McEwan et al., 2008). Cloning is further complicated as dinoflagellates are difficult to grow on solid media and a general transformation system for them is lacking (Rein and Borrone, 1999). Genetic transformation of only two dinoflagellates has been reported (ten Lohuis and Miller, 1998). No further attempts appear to have been made. The aforementioned

transformation involved a silicon carbide fiber-mediated introduction of bacterial genes fused with heterologous promoters in species of *Amphidinium* and *Symbiodinium* (ten Lohuis and Miller, 1998).

Gene–function mapping is of course essential for engineering improved production of bioactives. Unfortunately, the molecular genetics of the biosynthesis of dinoflagellate toxins is poorly understood (Kellmann et al., 2010), but progress is being made (Hu et al., 2010). Regulation of gene expression remains to be clarified. Dinoflagellate genes lack recognizable promoter features such as TATA boxes (a DNA sequence found in the promoter regions of eukaryote genes) and common eukaryotic transcription factor binding sites (Jaeckish et al., 2011). Transcriptional regulation of the genes is quite limited (Taroncher-Oldenburg and Anderson, 2000; Lin et al., 2010).

No particular phylogenetic trend is apparent among the toxin-producing dinoflagellate taxa, suggesting multiple independent evolutionary origins of the toxin production capability (Lin et al., 2011). The genes responsible for toxin synthesis occur within the chromosomes (Plumley, 1997; Taroncher-Oldenburg and Anderson, 2000), but exceptions have been reported. For example, a PKS gene sequence that is closely related to toxigenic cyanobacteria PKS genes has been found in *K. brevis* chloroplasts (López-Legentil et al., 2010).

Most of dinoflagellate toxins are likely produced via the polyketide pathway that involves a polyketide synthase (PKS) with some additional functional segments (Shimizu, 2003). Okadaic acid and the DTXs are essentially products of the polyketide pathway (Needham, 1994; Wright, 1996; MacPherson, 2003; Perez et al., 2008). Production of polyketides in all organisms appears to involve type I PKSs (Snyder et al., 2003). Gene clusters encoding PKS natural products have been identified in several marine bacteria (Salomon et al., 2004; Ramaswamy, 2007; Perez et al., 2008) some of which are known to be associated with dinoflagellates. Genes relating to the synthesis of PKS products have been

found in dinoflagellates such as *Karenia brevis* (Snyder et al., 2003; López-Legentil et al., 2010), *Amphidinium* sp. (Kubota et al., 2006) and *Prorocentrum lima* (Tang et al., 2009). Biosynthesis of polyketides is further discussed by Rein and Snyder (2006) and Kellmann et al. (2010).

The PSP toxins are believed to be made via a pathway involving arginine, S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) and acetate (Shimizu, 1996). SAM synthetase therefore likely plays a key role in STX biosynthesis (Lin, 2011). Paradoxically, homologs of SAM synthetase gene have been identified in both toxic and non-toxic dinoflagellates (Harlow et al., 2007).

3.3 Culture of dinoflagellates

Development of harmful algal blooms has attracted much attention and remains the focus of systematic studies of bloom dynamics. In contrast, barely any effort has been devoted to controlled culture of dinoflagellates in bioreactors. Production of large quantities of nondinoflagellate microalgae in photobioreactors has been quite successful (Molina Grima et al., 2003; Acién Fernández et al., 2005; Fernández Sevilla et al., 2010), but this has not been generally possible for dinoflagellate microalgae. Nonetheless, production of gram quantities of dinoflagellate bioactives for various purposes has mostly relied on culturing these microalgae in low productivity systems. The maximum biomass concentration attainable in a typical photosynthetic culture of a dinoflagellate is low (Hu et al., 2006; Mountfort et al., 2006; Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2010), for example, well below 1 g L^{-1} . Also, toxin production per cell is of the order of picograms (Shimizu, 2000); therefore, a photobioreactor culture typically has a low toxin productivity.

Dinoflagellates generally grow slower than the other microalgae, but the reasons for this are not clearly understood (Tang, 1996). The low growth rates of photosynthetic

dinoflagellates are unlikely to be related to any differences in the photosynthetic capacity relative to the other algae. For example, the chlorophyll *a* contents per unit mass of dinoflagellates are not significantly different than in the diatoms. In nutrient sufficient conditions, nonphotosynthesizing dinoflagellates, for example the heterotrophs, can grow more rapidly than the ones that rely exclusively on photosynthesis (Mendes, 2009; Skelton, 2009). To improve productivity of the desired bioactive in a bioreactor culture, several aspects of the producer organisms need to be first characterized. For example, methods need to be available for routine quantification of the bioactive and the life cycle of the producer strain and its nutritional requirements need to be understood. Nutrients provided in the culture medium may influence the cell specific production of the bioactive.

In nature, complex circadian systems control the behavior of dinoflagellates (Roenneberg and Merrow, 2002). For example, daylight and changes in the levels of nutrients in the water column, are known to condition vertical migrations (Doblin et al., 2006). In photosynthetic dinoflagellates, cells generally divide at the end of the dark period (Homma, 1989) and grow during the light phase. The latter corresponds to the G1 phase of the cell cycle. Production of many toxins has been found to coincide with the G1 phase (Taroncher-Oldenburg, 1998; Wong and Kwok, 2005). Dinoflagellates are able to couple the progression of the cell cycle to cell growth, enabling them to make the best use of available resources and possibly preparing them for a symbiotic existence (Wong and Kwok, 2005). In a photobioreactor where the levels of the nutrients are typically uniform and illumination is often continuous, the natural rhythms may breakdown and the metabolic behavior may be quite different to the behavior in nature.

Development of a capability to mass culture dinoflagellates for producing bioactives requires attention to the following points: 1) media formulations for enhancing cell growth and production of toxins; 2) optimization of the culture conditions to achieve high titers of the

desired bioactive in a short period; 3) elucidation of the possible triggers for the synthesis of toxins; and 4) better engineered photobioreactors. Some of these aspects have been discussed in the literature in relation to specific cases. For example, temperature has been shown to influence the saxitoxin content of *Alexandrium catenella* cells (Navarro et al., 2006) and the yessotoxin content of *P. reticulatum* cells (Paz et al., 2006). Environmental factors including osmotic pressure have been shown to affect the growth of *K. brevis* (Magaña and Villareal, 2006; Errera and Campbell, 2011).

The toxin profile of *Alexandrium ostenfeldii* has been found to be sensitive to the culture conditions (Otero et al., 2010). Nutritional supplementation of the culture medium has been found to influence the toxin productivity of several dinoflagellates (Wang and Hsieh, 2002; Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2009a). A two-step culture methodology has been found to improve toxin production by *Alexandrium tamarense* (Hu et al., 2006). The first step used 4-days of static conditions to favor growth. Subsequently, the culture was aerated in an airlift bioreactor (Hu et al., 2006). Similar strategies have been used in a stirred tank photobioreactor for producing toxins of *P. reticulatum* (Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2007).

Production of several dinoflagellate toxins in laboratory cultures has been discussed in the literature. The production of paralytic shellfish toxins has been reviewed by Hsieh et al. (2001). Production of yessotoxins has been described (Paz et al., 2004; Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2007). Other notable studies include: gymnodimine production by *Karenia selliformis* (Mountfort et al., 2006); production of C2 toxin by *Alexandrium tamarense* (Wang and Hsieh, 2002; Wang et al., 2002); saxitoxin production by *A. minutum* (Parker, 2002; Lim et al., 2010); ciguatoxin production by *Gambierdiscus polynesiensis* (Chinain, 2009); and palytoxin production by *Ostreopsis ovate* (Pistocchi et al., 2011).

Studies of toxin production in cultures have not generally used media developed specifically for maximizing the toxin productivity. The media formulations that are almost

exclusively used in culturing toxic dinoflagellates are the L1 (Guillard and Hargraves, 1993), the f/2 (Guillard, 1975) and the K medium (Keller and Guillard, 1986). These similar formulations were not originally developed for dinoflagellates. For example, the L1 medium was originally developed as a standard medium for culturing marine diatoms (Guillard and Hargraves, 1993). The commonly used formulations are therefore not necessarily optimal for the production of dinoflagellates and their toxins.

Medium development can dramatically impact the productivity of a metabolite. This has been demonstrated in industrial cultures of animal cells, for example (Wurm, 2004). Media for culturing dinoflagellates typically contain a large number of components. Optimizing such media by the conventional statistical experimental design is cumbersome. A superior alternative is to use optimization approaches based on genetic algorithms (GA) (Weuster-Botz, 2000). A genetic algorithm based stochastic search strategy has been used to successfully optimize the culture medium for producing yessotoxins from *P. reticulatum* (García-Camacho et al., 2011a). Optimization of the culture medium allowed a 60% enhancement in the final cell concentration relative to the control culture based on the L1 medium (García-Camacho et al., 2011a). The use of the optimized medium enhanced the productivity of yessotoxins by 40% relative to control and improved the stability of the cultures in the stationary phase (García-Camacho et al., 2011a).

Dinoflagellate culture at any significant scale inevitably requires the use of photobioreactors. The hydrodynamic environment in a photobioreactor is necessarily turbulent to ensure a homogeneous distribution of nutrients and cells. Turbulence is needed also to achieve mass transfer of carbon dioxide from the gas phase to the liquid phase at a sufficiently rapid rate. Dinoflagellates, unfortunately, are flow sensitive and tolerate only a limited level of turbulence as discussed next.

3.3.1 Flow sensitivity of dinoflagellates

Dinoflagellates are often sensitive to turbulence in the culture medium. Inhibition of growth by agitation, shaking, aeration and stirring has been commonly reported in laboratory cultures (e.g. White, 1976; Pollinger and Zemel, 1981; Berdalet, 1992). The growth rate and morphology are affected by small-scale turbulence (Berdalet and Estrada, 1993; Sullivan and Swift, 2003; Sullivan et al., 2003; Berdalet et al., 2007). In nature, the small-scale turbulence caused by winds and waves is known to adversely affect growth (Pollinger and Zemel, 1981; Berman and Shteinman, 1998; Stoecker et al., 2006). Consequently, a successful culture in a photobioreactor requires careful control of the turbulence intensity through engineering of the photobioreactor, a judicious selection of its operation regime and possible use of protective additives in the culture medium (Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2007; García Camacho et al., 2007b; Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2011).

Growth inhibition thresholds of the specific energy dissipation rates for various dinoflagellates are summarized in Table 2. The studies span several dinoflagellate orders and cell diameters ranging from 12 to 500 μm (Berdalet et al., 2007). No clear link has been established between the flow-sensitivity and the size, shape, and taxonomy of dinoflagellate species (Sullivan and Swift, 2003; Berdalet et al., 2007).

The reasons for the shear-sensitivity of dinoflagellates have been speculated on, but not definitively established. Dinoflagellates generally have large cells. In some species the cells may be as large as 2 mm. For photosynthetic species associated with the formation of harmful blooms, the size ranges approximately from 10 μm to 60 μm . Thecate dinoflagellates have a cell wall made of cellulosic plates, or thecae (Lee, 2008). The form and arrangement of the thecal plates varies with the species (Taylor et al., 2003). A cell protective function has been suggested for thecae (e.g. Thomas et al., 1997), but not supported by evidence: thecate dinoflagellates can be as sensitive to turbulence as athecate or naked species. For example, *P.*

reticulatum having thecae is highly shear-sensitive whereas *C. cohnii* having a similar cell wall structure is more robust. *P. reticulatum* is damaged by energy dissipation rate values exceeding $0.8 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ (García Camacho et al., 2007b), but *C. cohnii* can be grown at an energy dissipation rate of $5.8 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ without obvious damage (Hu et al., 2007).

Nanoindentation tests performed on thecal plates isolated from the dinoflagellates *Alexandrium catenella* and *Lingulodinium polyedrum* have shown these plates to have mechanical properties comparable to softwood cell walls (Lau et al., 2007). Many plant cells with cellulosic walls are of course known to be quite sensitive to hydrodynamic shear forces (Namdev and Dunlop, 1995; Joshi et al., 1996; Chisti, 2010) and plant cells also tend to be relatively large.

Figure 1 compares the damaging thresholds of energy dissipation reported for various orders of dinoflagellates and the average damage threshold reported for various kinds of animal cells cultured in bioreactors. Freely suspended animal cells in bioreactors are used in many commercial biotechnology processes and are among the most shear sensitive types of cells (Joshi et al., 1996; Chisti, 1999; Chisti, 2000; Juhl et al., 2000; Chisti, 2001). Suspended plant cells can also be sensitive to hydrodynamic stresses (Namdev and Dunlop, 1995; Joshi et al., 1996). Compared to such cells, dinoflagellates are much more sensitive to turbulence forces (Figure 1). In general, the shear stress levels that dinoflagellates can withstand are one or two orders of magnitude lower. Specific energy dissipation rate (ϵ) values in the range of $0.011 \leq \epsilon \leq 10 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ have generally inhibited dinoflagellate growth (Figure 1, Table 2). In studies that did not find an adverse effect of turbulence on dinoflagellate cells, the specific energy dissipation rate was always $<1 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ (Berdalet et al., 2007) and, therefore, not relevant to photobioreactor culture.

Flow sensitivity of dinoflagellates may be linked to their unusual genomes. Dinoflagellates possess enormous genomes packed in relatively small volumes. Their

genomes are in the range of 3–245 Gb, compared to 10–100 Mb for most of the other eukaryotic algae (Veldhuis et al., 1997). This is believed to increase the likelihood of entanglement of the DNA strands during replication (Wong and Kwok, 2005). The DNA in a dinoflagellate occurs mostly a liquid crystal state and may be susceptible to external mechanical stimuli transmitted to the nuclear envelope via the cytoskeleton. The nucleus is generally large, occupying nearly half of the cell volume, and this may increase the likelihood of transmission of the external mechanical forces to the nucleus. The chromosomes in the nucleus are not scattered, but are attached to the nuclear membrane. This may further enhance their susceptibility to mechanical stimuli. Such stimuli may provoke changes in the phase state of the DNA, leading to mutagenesis. This appears to explain the cell's increased susceptibility to shear forces at certain stages of the cell cycle (García Camacho et al., 2007b). Surprisingly, turbulence at certain levels appears to be able to reversibly arrest the progression of the cell cycle without causing cell death (Yeung and Wong, 2003). At lower levels, turbulence may merely slow the progression of the cell cycle rather than arrest it (Yeung and Wong, 2003).

Adverse responses to flow can be wide-ranging: growth inhibition, disturbance of the cell cycle (Berdalet, 1992; Yeung, 2003), production of peroxide radicals (Juhl and Latz, 2002; Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2009b), changes in the fluidity of the cell membrane (Mallipattu, 2002; Gallardo-Rodríguez et al., 2012), calcium mobilization (Yeung, 2006), and others. The magnitude of the response depends on the intensity of turbulence, its duration and the frequency of exposure. The light–dark cycle also affects how a cell responds to turbulence. Many kinds of cells are known to adapt to better withstand shear stresses, but this does not appear to be so for dinoflagellates such as *P. reticulatum* (García Camacho et al., 2007b). The intensity of shear stress appears to influence the production of toxins in at least some dinoflagellates (Juhl et al., 2001; Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2011).

Some of the above mentioned effects of turbulence are interdependent. The molecular basis of mechanochemical transduction of external shear stress into the cell remains largely unclear. The cytoskeleton may have a role in mechanochemical transduction of external forces, but does not seem to be the primary sensor of flow. In animal cells, lipid bilayers of cell membranes are said to possess flow-sensing receptors (Gudi et al., 1996) and a similar mechanism may exist in the outer plasma membrane of dinoflagellates. In animal cells, changes in the fluid shear stress level are known to alter the membrane viscosity. A similar phenomena may occur in dinoflagellates. For example, supplementation of the culture medium with additives that reduce the fluidity of the cell membrane, has been shown to protect animal cells against shear stresses. Similar additives have the potential to extend the shear tolerance range of dinoflagellates, to improve their cultivability.

Many studies of shear sensitivity either failed to satisfactorily quantify the turbulence intensity, or used experimental systems that were not particularly meaningful in the context of culture in a photobioreactor. Studies have been reported mostly in Couette flow devices, shakers and oscillating rod mixers. The uniform and better defined shear field in a Couette flow certainly facilitates data analysis, but the cells are not subjected to the full range of stresses found in a typical photobioreactor. Furthermore, a photobioreactor typically requires a supply of carbon dioxide and bubbling gas through the culture fluid affects the hydrodynamic forces experienced by the cells (Chisti, 2000).

In a Couette flow device, growth of the heterotrophic dinoflagellate *Cryptocodinium cohnii* was inhibited at relatively low energy dissipation rate values of $0.1\text{--}1.0\text{ cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-3}$ (Yeung and Wong, 2003), but this organism is known to be exceptional among dinoflagellates in withstanding fairly turbulent conditions in bioreactors. For example, Hu et al. (2007) found *C. cohnii* to tolerate energy dissipation rates of up to $5.8\times 10^5\text{ cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-3}$ without lysis. Indeed, *C.*

cohnii is used in industrial production of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) in bioreactors (Mendes et al., 2009).

Unlike Couette flow devices, shaken flasks subject the cells to a hydrodynamic environment that is closer to that of a photobioreactor. Shake flasks have proven useful for rapidly screening microbial cultures and identifying the suitable growth conditions (Suresh et al., 2009). Methods have been developed for estimating the hydrodynamic stresses experienced by cells suspended in shake flasks (Peter et al., 2006).

3.3.2 Bioreactor culture

Bulk average specific energy dissipation rates (ε_{ave}) in bubble columns and industrial-scale stirred tanks vary commonly in the range of $1,000 \leq \varepsilon_{\text{ave}} \leq 40,000 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ (Chisti, 1999; Chisti, 2000). These values of ε_{ave} far exceed the damage thresholds for toxic dinoflagellates (Figure 1). Furthermore, the local value of ε in a bioreactor can greatly exceed the average rate of energy dissipation. For example, the local specific energy dissipation rate behind a rupturing bubble and in the vicinity of an impeller, can be much greater than the average specific energy dissipation rate for the bioreactor. Therefore conventional regimes of operation of bubble columns and stirred tank photobioreactors are not suitable for culturing most dinoflagellates, but exceptions exist. For example, *P. reticulatum* has been found to be sensitive to turbulence in bioreactors (García Camacho et al., 2007b), but this does not seem to be the case for *Alexandrium minutum* (Parker, 2002).

Culture of shear-sensitive cells in a stirred tank is often possible so long as the bioreactor has a suitable geometry and the regime of operation is carefully chosen (Chisti, 2000; Chisti, 2010). Characterization of turbulence intensity in terms of shear rate and shear stress in various kinds of bioreactors has been discussed in the literature (Chisti, 1999; Chisti, 2001; Sánchez Pérez et al., 2006; Chisti, 2010; Merchuk and Garcia-Camacho, 2010). In

aerated cultures, gas bubbles have the potential to damage sensitive cells, but methods have been developed to limit the damage (Chisti, 2000; Gallardo Rodríguez et al., 2011). High pressure has been linked to changes in thecal plate pattern and microtubule assembly of the dinoflagellate *Scrippsiella hexapraeicingula* (Sekida et al., 2012).

Although the methods for design and scale up of photobioreactor are well established for microalgae that are relatively physically robust (Molina et al., 2001), these methods cannot be translated to culturing the fragile dinoflagellates. As for any algal culture, penetration of light in the photobioreactor is an important issue also for dinoflagellate culture. Consequently, the diameter of the bioreactor vessels can be increased only to a limited extent, or the availability of light will be reduced to unacceptably low levels. In addition, the ability to mix the culture is severely limited by the shear damage threshold considerations. Thus, a low-shear impeller must be used in a vessel that is relatively narrow and tall to accommodate the required volume.

A further complicating factor is mass transfer: the photosynthetically generated oxygen must be removed, but the conventional method of removing the oxygen by bubbling the algal broth with air, is not generally applicable as the gas bubbles rupturing at the surface of the broth are extremely damaging to fragile cells (Chisti, 2000). For example, mixing and oxygen removal by bubbling the broth with air have been found to be impossible with *P. reticulatum* (García Camacho et al., 2007b). Either the oxygen must be removed via desorption from the surface of the broth in the tank, or the cells must be excluded from a certain volume of the broth, for example, by using a spinfilter (Chisti, 2000; García Camacho et al., 2011b) so that the cell-free volume of the broth can be sparged with air to remove the oxygen. Oxygen removal from the surface becomes increasingly difficult as the volume of the broth is increased in a vessel of a relatively narrow diameter.

Design and operation of a photobioreactor for a dinoflagellate require an initial characterization of its susceptibility to turbulence. Studies in shake flasks can be quite useful for this. For example, shake flasks were used to identify an average energy dissipation rate (ϵ_{ave}) value of $0.8 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ as the damage threshold for the dinoflagellate *P. reticulatum* (García Camacho et al., 2007b). As *P. reticulatum* does not withstand gas bubbles, gas sparged bioreactors were ruled out. This guided the choice to a surface aerated 2 L stirred tank bioreactor equipped with a low-shear axial flow impeller and a central spinfilter (Gallardo Rodriguez et al., 2007; Gallardo Rodriguez et al., 2010). The local value of the maximum specific energy dissipation rate (ϵ_{max}) in the bioreactor was $1.49 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ (García Camacho et al., 2011b), or higher than the damage threshold, but this did not pose a problem because the cells were exposed to damaging turbulence only for a brief period during circulation in the bioreactor. The average value of the specific energy dissipation rate in the bioreactor was only $0.3 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$ (García Camacho et al., 2011b), or much lower than the earlier noted damage threshold. The data obtained were used to further scale up the production to a 15 L stirred bioreactor (García Camacho et al., 2011b).

In the larger reactor, the vessel diameter could not be much greater than in the 2 L bioreactor, or light supply would have limited. Thus, the 15 L stirred photobioreactor for suspension culture of *P. reticulatum* was designed to be tall and slender with an aspect ratio of 4.5 (García Camacho et al., 2011b). Two scaling-up criteria were considered in designing this photobioreactor (García Camacho et al., 2011b). The first criterion related with the frequency of passage of the cells through the high-shear zone of the impeller, or the inverse of the circulation time in the photobioreactor. The second scaling-up criterion consisted of keeping the tip speed of the impeller at the 15 L scale at the same value as was successfully used at the 2 L scale. The tip speed is related to the maximum specific energy dissipation rate (ϵ_{max}) in a stirred tank. In the taller bioreactor, the impeller-to-tank diameter ratio was kept at

nearly the same value as in the smaller bioreactor. This led to an impeller diameter of 8.14 cm in the larger vessel. An impeller of this size rotating at 50 rpm would have an acceptable tip speed of $0.2 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ ($\varepsilon_{\text{ave}} \approx 0.007 \text{ cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-3}$; $\varepsilon_{\text{max}} = 4.77 \text{ cm}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-3}$), but the circulation time would be eight times as high as in the small reactor. A lowering of the circulation time by increasing the rotation speed would result in an excessively high value of ε_{max} (García Camacho et al., 2011b).

Of course, a high circulation time reduces the frequency of passage of the cells through the high-shear zone of the impeller, but provokes other issues. For example, the gas–liquid mass transfer is poorer at high values of the circulation time. This leads to an increased oxygen accumulation in the culture broth and an increased formation of the reactive oxygen species (ROS). Oxygen accumulation at a lower impeller speed could be reduced by bubbling the region within the spinfilter at a high value of the aeration rate. In addition, the culture medium was supplemented with ascorbic acid to protect the cells against damage by the reactive oxygen species. Although the scale-up to 15 L proved successful, further scale-up to larger bioreactors does not seem possible for *P. reticulatum* unless the culture medium is formulated with effective shear-protective additives.

4. Concluding remarks

Dinoflagellate microalgae can provide numerous potentially useful bioactives. Relatively few of such products have been investigated because of a limited supply from nature. Large scale chemical synthesis of most of these products is exceedingly complex. Dinoflagellate culture in photobioreactors appears to be the only realistic option for producing quantities of bioactives of interest. In view of their extreme sensitivity to turbulence, many dinoflagellates are impossibly difficult to culture in bioreactors. Nevertheless, the culture

methodology and photobioreactor designs are being developed to make relatively large scale production of biomass and toxins feasible.

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References

- Acién Fernández FG, Fernández Sevilla JM, Egorova-Zachernyuk TA, Molina Grima E. Cost-effective production of ¹³C, ¹⁵N stable isotope-labeled biomass from phototrophic microalgae for various biotechnological applications. *Biomol Eng* 2005;22:193-200.
- Adachi M. The identification of conspecific dinoflagellates *Alexandrium tamarense* from Japan and Thailand by monoclonal antibodies. *Nippon Suisan Gakk* 1993;59:327-32.
- Adachi M, Sako Y, Ishida Y. Identification of the toxic dinoflagellates *Alexandrium catenella* and *A. tamarense* (Dinophyceae) using DNA probes and whole-cell hybridization. *J Phycol* 1996;32:1049-52.
- Anderson DM. Identification of harmful algal species using molecular probes: An emerging perspective. In: Lassus P, Arzul G, Erard E, Gentien P, Marcaillou C, editors. *Harmful marine algal blooms*. Paris: Lavoisier; 1995. p. 3-13.
- Anderson DM. Approaches to monitoring, control and management of harmful algal blooms (HABs). *Ocean Coast Manage* 2009;52:342-47.
- Bachvaroff TR. Dinoflagellate expressed sequence tag data indicate massive transfer of chloroplast genes to the nuclear genome. *Protist* 2004;155:65-78.

- Berdalet E. Effects of turbulence on the marine dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium nelsonii*. J Phycol 1992;28:267-72.
- Berdalet E, Estrada M. Effects of turbulence on several dinoflagellate species. In: Smayda TJ, Shimizu Y, editors. Toxic phytoplankton blooms in the sea. New York: Elsevier; 1993. p. 737-740.
- Berdalet E, Peters F, Koumandou VL, Roldan C, Guadayol O, Estrada M. Species-specific physiological response of dinoflagellates to quantified small-scale turbulence. J Phycol 2007;43:965-77.
- Berman T, Shteinman B. Phytoplankton development and turbulent mixing in Lake Kinneret (1992-1996). J Plankton Res 1998;20:709-26.
- Blunt JW, Copp BR, Hu W-P, Munro MHG, Northcote PT, Prinsep MR. Marine natural products. Nat Prod Rep 2009;26:170-244.
- Bowers HA, Tengs T, Glasgow HB, Burkholder JM, Rublee PA, Oldach DW. Development of real-time PCR assays for rapid detection of *Pfiesteria piscicida* and related dinoflagellates. Appl Environ Microb 2000;66:4641-48.
- Chinain M. Growth and toxin production in the ciguatera-causing dinoflagellate *Gambierdiscus polynesiensis* (Dinophyceae) in culture. Toxicon 2009;56:739-50.
- Chisti Y. Shear sensitivity. Encyclopedia of Bioprocess Technology: Fermentation, Biocatalysis, and Bioseparation 1999;5:2379-406.
- Chisti, Y. Strategies in downstream processing. In: Subramanian G, editor. Bioseparation and bioprocessing: A handbook. Vol. 1, 2nd ed. New York: Wiley-VCH; 2007. p. 29-62.
- Chisti Y. Shear sensitivity. Encyclopedia of Industrial Biotechnology, Bioprocess, Bioseparation, and Cell Technology 2010;7:4360-98.
- Chisti Y. Animal-cell damage in sparged bioreactors. Trends Biotechnol 2000;18:420-32.
- Chisti, Y. Hydrodynamic damage to animal cells. Crit Rev Biotechnol 2001;21:67-110.

- Cho ES, Costas E. Rapid monitoring for the potentially ichthyotoxic dinoflagellate *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* in Korean coastal waters using fluorescent probe tools. *J Plankton Res* 2004;26:175-80.
- Crimmins MT, McDougall PJ, Ellis JM. Improved synthesis of the ABCDE fragment of brevetoxin A. *Org Lett* 2006;8:4079-82.
- Dempsey HP. The effects of turbulence on three algae. *Skeletonema costatum*, *Gonyaulax tamarensis*, *Heterocapsa triquetra*. SB Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts; 1982.
- Doblin MA, Thompson PA, Revill AT, Butler ECV, Blackburn SI, Hallegraeff GM. Vertical migration of the toxic dinoflagellate *Gymnodinium catenatum* under different concentrations of nutrients and humic substances in culture. *Harmful Algae* 2006;5:665-77.
- Dunlap WC, Battershill CN, Liptrot CH, Cobb RE, Bourne DG, Jaspars M, Long PF, Newman DJ. Biomedicinals from the phytosymbionts of marine invertebrates: A molecular approach. *Methods* 2007;42:358-76.
- Errera RM, Campbell L. Osmotic stress triggers toxin production by the dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis*. *P Natl Acad Sci USA* 2011;108:10597-601.
- Faulkner DJ. Marine pharmacology. *Anton Leeuw Int J G* 2000;77:135-45.
- Fernández JJ, Candenás ML, Souto ML, Trujillo MM, Norte M. Okadaic acid, useful tool for studying cellular processes. *Curr Med Chem* 2002;9:229-62.
- Fernández Sevilla JM, Acién Fernández FG, Molina Grima E. Biotechnological production of lutein and its applications. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 2010;86:27-40.
- Franchina A, Marchesini E, Poletti R, Ottaviani E. Swiss mice CD1 fed on mussels contaminated by okadaic acid and yessotoxins: effects on thymus and spleen. *Eur J Histochem* 2005;49:179-88.

- Fuwa H, Sasaki M. Recent advances in the synthesis of marine polycyclic ether natural products. *Curr Opin Drug Disc* 2007;10:784-806.
- Fürstner A, Flugge S, Larionov O, Takahashi Y, Kubota T, Kobayashi J. Total synthesis and biological evaluation of amphidinolide V and analogues. *Chem-Eur J* 2009;15:4011-29.
- Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Cerón García, M-C, García Camacho F, Sánchez Mirón A, Belarbi EH, Molina Grima E. New culture approaches for yessotoxin production from the dinoflagellate *Protoceratium reticulatum*. *Biotechnol Progr* 2007;23:339-50.
- Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez Mirón A, Cerón García M-C, Belarbi EH, García Camacho F, Chisti Y, Molina Grima E. Macronutrients requirements of the dinoflagellate *Protoceratium reticulatum*. *Harmful Algae* 2009a;8:239-46.
- Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez Mirón A, Cerón García M-C, Belarbi EH, García Camacho F, Chisti Y, Molina Grima E. Causes of shear sensitivity of the toxic dinoflagellate *Protoceratium reticulatum*. *Biotechnol Progr* 2009b;25:792-800.
- Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez Mirón A, García Camacho F, Cerón García MC, Belarbi EH, Molina Grima E. Culture of dinoflagellates in a fed-batch and continuous stirred-tank photobioreactors: Growth, oxidative stress and toxin production. *Process Biochem* 2010;45:660-66.
- Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez Mirón A, García Camacho F, Cerón García MC, Belarbi EH, Chisti Y, Molina Grima E. Carboxymethyl cellulose and Pluronic F68 protect the dinoflagellate *Protoceratium reticulatum* against shear-associated damage. *Bioproc Biosyst Eng* 2011;34:3-12.
- Gallardo-Rodríguez JJ, García-Camacho F, Sánchez-Mirón A, López-Rosales L, Chisti Y, Molina-Grima E. Shear-induced changes in membrane fluidity during culture of a fragile dinoflagellate microalga. *Biotechnol Progr* 2012;28:467-73.

- Galluzzi L, Cegna A, Casabianca S, Penna A, Saunders N, Magnani M. Development of an oligonucleotide microarray for the detection and monitoring of marine dinoflagellates. *J Microbiol Meth* 2011;84:234-42.
- García Camacho F, Gallardo Rodríguez J, Sánchez Mirón A, Cerón García MC, Belarbi EH, Chisti Y, Molina Grima E. Biotechnological significance of toxic marine dinoflagellates. *Biotechnol Adv* 2007a;25:176-94.
- García Camacho F, Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez Mirón A, Cerón García MC, Molina Grima E. Determination of shear stress thresholds in toxic dinoflagellates cultured in shaken flasks. Implications in bioprocess engineering. *Process Biochem* 2007b;42:1506-15.
- García-Camacho F, Gallardo-Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez-Mirón A, Chisti Y, Molina-Grima E. Genetic algorithm-based medium optimization for a toxic dinoflagellate microalga. *Harmful Algae* 2011b;10:697-701.
- García Camacho F, Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez Mirón A, Belarbi EH, Chisti Y, Molina Grima E. Photobioreactor scale-up for a shear-sensitive dinoflagellate microalga. *Process Biochem* 2011b;46:936-44.
- Gas F. Monoclonal antibody against the surface of *Alexandrium minutum* used in a whole-cell ELISA. *Harmful Algae* 2009;8:538-45.
- Gibson CH, Thomas WH. Effects of turbulence intermittency on growth inhibition of a red tide dinoflagellate, *Gonyaulax polyedra* Stein. *J Geophys Res-Oceans* 1995;100(C12):24841-46.
- Glaser KB. A renaissance in marine pharmacology: From preclinical curiosity to clinical reality. *Biochem Pharmacol* 2009;78:440-8.

- Gudi SRP, Clark CB, Frangos JA. Fluid flow rapidly activates G proteins in human endothelial cells: Involvement of G proteins in mechanochemical signal transduction. *Circ Res* 1996;79:834-9.
- Guillard RRL. Culture of phytoplankton for feeding marine invertebrates. In: Smith WL, Chanley MH, editors. *Culture of marine invertebrate animals*. New York: Plenum Press; 1975. p. 26-60.
- Guillard RRL, Hargraves PE. *Stichochrysis immobilis* is a diatom, not a chrysophyte. *Phycologia* 1993;32:234-6.
- Haefner B. Drugs from the deep: Marine natural products as drug candidates. *Drug Discov Today* 2003;8:536-44.
- Hackett JD. Migration of the plastid genome to the nucleus in a peridinin dinoflagellate. *Curr Biol* 2004;14:213-8.
- Hackett JD, Scheetz TE, Yoon HS, Soares MB, Bonaldo MF, Casavant TL, Bhattacharya D. Insights into a dinoflagellate genome through expressed sequence tag analysis. *BMC Genomics* 2005;6: article 80.
- Hagen NA, Fisher KM, Lapointe B, du Souich P, Chary S, Moulin D, Sellers E, Ngoc AH. An open-label, multi-dose efficacy and safety study of intramuscular tetrodotoxin in patients with severe cancer-related pain. *J Pain Symptom Manag* 2007;34:171-82.
- Hagen NA, du Souich P, Lapointe B, Ong-Lam M, Dubuc B, Walde D. Tetrodotoxin for moderate to severe cancer pain: A randomized, double-blind, parallel design multicenter study. *J Pain Symptom Manag* 2008;35:420-9.
- Hallegraeff GM. Harmful algal blooms: A global overview. In: Hallegraeff GM, Anderson DM, Cembella AD, editors. *Manual on harmful marine microalgae*. Paris: UNESCO Publishing; 2003. p. 25-49.

- Harlow LD, Koutoulis A, Hallegraef GM. S-adenosylmethionine synthetase genes from eleven marine dinoflagellates. *Phycologia* 2007;46:46-53.
- Havskum H. Effects of small-scale turbulence on interactions between the heterotrophic dinoflagellate *Oxyrrhis marina* and its prey, *Isochrysis* sp. *Ophelia* 2003;57(3):125-35.
- Havskum H, Hansen PJ, Berdalet E. Effect of turbulence on sedimentation and net population growth of the dinoflagellate *Ceratium tripos* and interactions with its predator, *Fragilidium subglobosum*. *Limnol Oceanogr* 2005;50:1543-51.
- Hirama M. Total synthesis of ciguatoxin CTX3C: A venture into the problems of ciguatera seafood poisoning. *Chem Rec* 2005;5:240-50.
- Holland PT, Shi F, Satake M, Hamamoto Y, Ito E, Beuzenberg V, McNabb P, Munday R, Briggs L, Truman P, Gooneratne R, Edwards P, Pascal SM. Novel toxins produced by the dinoflagellate *Karenia brevisulcata*. *Harmful Algae* 2012;13:47-57.
- Homma K. The S phase is discrete and is controlled by the circadian clock in the marine dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax polyedra*. *Exp Cell Res* 1989;182:635-44.
- Hsieh DPH, Wang D, Chang GH. Laboratory bioproduction of paralytic shellfish toxins in dinoflagellates. *Adv Appl Microbiol* 2001;49:85-110.
- Hu H, Shi Y, Cong W. Improvement in growth and toxin production of *Alexandrium tamarense* by two-step culture method. *J Appl Phycol* 2006;18:119-26.
- Hu W, Gladue R, Hansen J, Wojnar C, Chalmers JJ. The sensitivity of the dinoflagellate *Cryptocodinium cohnii* to transient hydrodynamic forces and cell-bubble interactions. *Biotechnol Progr* 2007;23:1355-62.
- Hu W-M, Xu J, Sinkkonen J, Wu J. Polyketides from marine dinoflagellates of the genus *Prorocentrum*, biosynthetic origin and bioactivity of their okadaic acid analogues. *Mini-Rev Med Chem* 2010;10:51-61.

- Humpage AR, Magalhaes VF, Froscio SM. Comparison of analytical tools and biological assays for detection of paralytic shellfish poisoning toxins. *Anal Bioanal Chem* 2010;397:1655-71.
- Islam MM, Begum S, Lin L, Okamura A, Du M, Fujimura S. Synergistic cytotoxic effect between serine-threonine phosphatase inhibitors and 5-fluorouracil: A novel concept for modulation of cytotoxic effect. *Cancer Chemoth Pharm* 2002;49:111-8.
- Ito E, Satake M, Ofuji K, Kurita N, McMahon T, James K, Yasumoto T. Multiple organ damage caused by a new toxin azaspiracid, isolated from mussels produced in Ireland. *Toxicon* 2000;38:917-30.
- Ito E, Satake M, Ofuji K, Higashi M, Harigaya K, McMahon T, Yasumoto T. Chronic effects in mice caused by oral administration of sublethal doses of azaspiracid, a new marine toxin isolated from mussels. *Toxicon* 2002;40:193-203.
- Jaeckisch N, Yang I, Wohlrab S, Glöckner G, Kroymann J, Vogel H, Cembella A, John U. Comparative genomic and transcriptomic characterization of the toxigenic marine dinoflagellate *Alexandrium ostenfeldii*. *PLoS One* 2001;6:e28012.
- Joshi JB, Elias CB, Patole MS. Role of hydrodynamic shear in the cultivation of animal, plant and microbial cells. *Chem Eng J Bioch Eng* 1996;62:121-41.
- Juhl AR, Latz MI. Mechanisms of fluid shear-induced inhibition of population growth in a red-tide dinoflagellate. *J Phycol* 2002;38:683-94.
- Juhl AR, Trainer VL, Latz MI. Effect of fluid shear and irradiance on population growth and cellular toxin content of the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium fundyense*. *Limnol Oceanogr* 2001;46:758-64.
- Juhl AR, Velazquez V, Latz MI. Effect of growth conditions on flow-induced inhibition of population growth of a red-tide dinoflagellate. *Limnol Oceanogr* 2000;45:905-15.

- Keller MD, Guillard RRL. Factors significant to marine dinoflagellate culture. In: Anderson DM, White AW, Baden DG, editors. Toxic dinoflagellates. New York: Elsevier; 1986. p. 113-116.
- Kellmann R, Stuken A, Orr RJS, Svendsen HM, Jakobsen KS. Biosynthesis and molecular genetics of polyketides in marine dinoflagellates. *Mar Drugs* 2010;8:1011-48.
- Kim YS, Ahn KH, Kim SY, Jeong JW. Okadaic acid promotes angiogenesis via activation of hypoxia-inducible factor-1. *Cancer Letters* 2009;276:102-8.
- Kobayashi J, Kubota T. Bioactive macrolides and polyketides from marine dinoflagellates of the genus *Amphidinium*. *J Nat Prod* 2007;70:451-60.
- Kobayashi J, Shimbo K, Kubota T, Tsuda M. Bioactive macrolides and polyketides from marine dinoflagellates. *Pure Appl Chem* 2003;75:337-42.
- Kubota T, Iinuma Y, Kobayashi J. Cloning of polyketide synthase genes from amphidinolide-producing dinoflagellate *Amphidinium* sp. *Biol Pharm Bull* 2006;29:1314-18.
- Kudela RM, Howard MDA, Jenkins BD, Miller PE, Smith GJ. Using the molecular toolbox to compare harmful algal blooms in upwelling systems. *Prog Oceanogr* 2010;85:108-21.
- Lau RKL, Kwok ACM, Chan WK, Zhang TY, Wong JTY. Mechanical characterization of cellulosic thecal plates in dinoflagellates by nanoindentation. *J Nanosci Nanotechnol* 2007;7:452-7.
- Lee RE. *Phycology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2008.
- Lim P-T, Leaw C-P, Kobiyama A, Ogata T. Growth and toxin production of tropical *Alexandrium minutum* Halim (Dinophyceae) under various nitrogen to phosphorus ratios. *J Appl Phycol* 2010;22:203-10.
- Lin S-J. Genomic understanding of dinoflagellates. *Res Microbiol* 2011;162:551-69.

- Lin S, Zhang H, Zhuang Y, Tran B, Gill J. Spliced leader-based metatranscriptomic analyses lead to recognition of hidden genomic features in dinoflagellates. *P Natl Acad Sci USA* 2010;107:20033-8.
- Litaker RW, Tester PA. Molecular methods for detecting and characterizing harmful phytoplankton. In: Hurst CJ, Crawford RL, Knudsen GR, McInerney MJ, Stetzenbach LD, editors. *Manual of environmental microbiology*. 2nd ed. Washington, DC: American Society for Microbiology Press; 2002. p. 342-353.
- López-Legentil S, Song B, DeTure M, Baden DG. Characterization and localization of a hybrid non-ribosomal peptide synthetase and polyketide synthase gene from the toxic dinoflagellate *Karenia brevis*. *Mar Biotechnol* 2010;12:32-41.
- MacPherson GR. Studies of the biosynthesis of DTX-5a and DTX-5b by the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum maculosum*: Regiospecificity of the putative Baeyer-Villigerase and insertion of a single amino acid in a polyketide chain. *J Org Chem* 2003;68:1659-64.
- Magaña HA, Villareal TA. The effect of environmental factors on the growth rate of *Karenia brevis* (Davis) G. Hansen and Moestrup. *Harmful Algae* 2006;5:192-8.
- Majumder U, Cox JM, Johnson HWB, Rainier JD. Total synthesis of gambierol: The generation of the A-C and F-H subunits by using a C-glycoside centered strategy. *Chem-Eur J* 2006;12:1736-46.
- Mallipattu SK. Evidence for shear-induced increase in membrane fluidity in the dinoflagellate *Lingulodinium polyedrum*. *J Comp Physiol A* 2002;188:409-16.
- Martín López A, Gallardo Rodríguez JJ, Sánchez Mirón A, García Camacho F, Molina Grima E. Immunoregulatory potential of marine algal toxins yessotoxin and okadaic acid in mouse T lymphocyte cell line EL-4. *Toxicol Lett* 2011;207:167-72.
- McEwan M, Humayun R, Slamovits CH, Keeling PJ. Nuclear genome sequence survey of the dinoflagellate *Heterocapsa triquetra*. *J Eukaryot Microbiol* 2008;55:530-5.

- Mendes A. *Crypthecodinium cohnii* with emphasis on DHA production: A review. *J Appl Phycol* 2009;21:199-214.
- Mendes A, Reis A, Vasconcelos R, Guerra P, Lopes Da Silva T. *Crypthecodinium cohnii* with emphasis on DHA production: A review. *J Appl Phycol* 2009;21:199-214.
- Mendoza H, Lopez-Rodas V, Gonzalez-Gil S, Aguilera A, Costas E. The use of polyclonal antisera and blocking of antibodies in the identification of marine dinoflagellates: Species-specific and clone-specific antisera against *Gymnodinium* and *Alexandrium*. *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol* 1995;186:103-15.
- Merchuk JC, García-Camacho F. Bioreactors, airlift reactors. *Encyclopedia of Industrial Biotechnology: Bioprocess, Bioseparation, and Cell Technology* 2010;2:851-912.
- Michelliza S, Abraham WM, Jacocks HM, Schuster T, Baden DG. Synthesis, modeling, and biological evaluation of analogues of the semisynthetic brevetoxin antagonist β -naphthoyl-brevetoxin. *ChemBioChem* 2007;8:2233-9.
- Molina E, Fernández J, Acién FG, Chisti Y. Tubular photobioreactor design for algal cultures. *J Biotechnol* 2001;92:113-31.
- Molina Grima E, Belarbi EH, Acién Fernández FG, Robles Medina A, Chisti Y. Recovery of microalgal biomass and metabolites: Process options and economics. *Biotechnol Adv* 2003;20:491-515.
- Moore SK, Mantua NJ, Hickey BM, Trainer VL. Recent trends in paralytic shellfish toxins in Puget Sound, relationships to climate, and capacity for prediction of toxic events. *Harmful Algae* 2009;8:463-77.
- Moore SK, Trainer VL, Mantua NJ, Parker MS, Laws EA, Backer LC, Fleming LE. Impacts of climate variability and future climate change on harmful algal blooms and human health. *Environmental Health* 2008;7: article S4.

- Moreno Díaz de la Espina S, Alverca E, Cuadrado A, Franca S. Organization of the genome and gene expression in a nuclear environment lacking histones and nucleosomes: The amazing dinoflagellates. *Eur J Cell Biol* 2005;84:137-49.
- Morita M, Ishiyama S, Koshino H, Nakata T. Synthetic studies on maitotoxin. 1. Stereoselective synthesis of the C D E F-ring system having a side chain. *Org Lett* 2008a;10:1675-78.
- Morita M, Haketa T, Koshino H, Nakata T. Synthetic studies on maitotoxin. 2. Stereoselective synthesis of the WXYZA-ring system. *Org Lett* 2008b;10:1679-82.
- Morita T, MacGregor JT, Hayashi M. Micronucleus assays in rodent tissues other than bone marrow. *Mutagenesis* 2011;26:223-30.
- Mountfort D, Beuzenberg V, MacKenzie L, Rhodes L. Enhancement of growth and gymnodimine production by the marine dinoflagellate, *Karenia selliformis*. *Harmful Algae* 2006;5:658-64.
- Murakami K, Tamura O, Ono T. Red tide-causing alga exterminating agent and red tide protective method using the same. Japan Patent Application JP 2006-36746; 2006.
- Nakata T. Total synthesis of marine polycyclic ethers. *Chem Rev* 2005;105:4314-47.
- Namdev PK, Dunlop EH. Shear sensitivity of plant cells in suspensions present and future. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol* 1995;54:109-31.
- Navarro JM, Muñoz MG, Contreras AM. Temperature as a factor regulating growth and toxin content in the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella*. *Harmful Algae* 2006;5:762-9.
- Needham J. Biosynthetic origin of C-37 and C-38 in the polyether toxins okadaic acid and dinophysistoxin-1. *J Chem Soc Chem Comm* 1994;22:2599-600.
- Neilan BA, Mihali TK, Kellmann R, Jeon YJ. Cyanobacteria saxitoxin gene cluster and detection of cyanotoxic organisms. US Patent Application 2011129842; 2011.

- Nicholas GM, Phillips AJ. Marine natural products: Synthetic aspects. *Nat Prod Rep* 2006;23:79-99.
- Nicolaou KC, Reddy KR, Skokotas G, Sato F, Xiao XY, Hwang CK. Total synthesis of hemibrevetoxin B and (7 α)-epi-hemibrevetoxin B. *J Am Chem Soc* 1993;115:3558-75.
- Nicolaou KC, Rutjes FPJT, Theodorakis EA, Tiebes J, Sato M, Untersteller E. Total synthesis of brevetoxin B. 3. Final strategy and completion. *J Am Chem Soc* 1995;117:10252-63.
- Nicolaou KC, Gunzner JL, Shi GQ, Agrios KA, Gartner P, Yang Z. Total synthesis of brevetoxin A: Part 4: Final stages and completion. *Chem-Eur J* 1999;5:646-58.
- Nicolaou KC, Vyskocil S, Koftis TV, Yamada YMA, Ling TT, Chen DYK, Tang WJ, Petrovic G, Frederick MO, Li YW, Satake M. Structural revision and total synthesis of azaspiracid-1, Part 1: Intelligence gathering and tentative proposal 13. *Angew Chem Int Edit* 2004a;43:4312-8.
- Nicolaou KC, Koftis TV, Vyskocil S, Petrovic G, Ling TT, Yamada YMA, Tang WJ, Frederick MO. Structural revision and total synthesis of azaspiracid-1, Part 2: Definition of the ABCD domain and total synthesis 13. *Angew Chem Int Edit* 2004b;43:4318-24.
- Oishi T, Suzuki M, Watanabe K, Murata M. Convergent synthesis of the CDEF ring fragment of yessotoxin via α -cyano ethers. *Heterocycles* 2006;69:91-8.
- Okamoto OK, Hastings JW. Novel dinoflagellate clock-related genes identified through microarray analysis. *J Phycol* 2003;39:519-26.
- Otero P, Alfonso A, Vieytes MR, Cabado AG, Vieites JM, Botana LM. Effects of environmental regimens on the toxin profile of *Alexandrium ostenfeldii*. *Environ Toxicol Chem* 2010;29:301-10.

- Parker NS. Growth of the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium minutum* (Dinophyceae) using high biomass culture systems. *J Appl Phycol* 2002;14:313-24.
- Paul III JH. Detection of polyketide synthetase gene expression in *Karenia brevis*. US Patent 7,888,031; 2011.
- Paz B, Riobó P, Luisa Fernández M, Fraga S, Franco JM. Production and release of yessotoxins by the dinoflagellates *Protoceratium reticulatum* and *Lingulodinium polyedrum* in culture. *Toxicon* 2004;44:251-8.
- Paz B, Vázquez JA, Riobó P, Franco JM. Study of the effect of temperature, irradiance and salinity on growth and yessotoxin production by the dinoflagellate *Protoceratium reticulatum* in culture by using a kinetic and factorial approach. *Mar Environ Res* 2006;62:286-300.
- Peperzak L, Vrieling EG, Sandee B, Rutten T. Immuno flow cytometry in marine phytoplankton research. *Sci Mar* 2000;64:165-81.
- Perez R, Liu L, Lopez J, An T, Rein KS. Diverse bacterial PKS sequences derived from okadaic acid-producing dinoflagellates. *Mar Drugs* 2008;6:164-79.
- Peter CP, Suzuki Y, Büchs J. Hydromechanical stress in shake flasks: Correlation for the maximum local energy dissipation rate. *Biotechnol Bioeng* 2006;93:1164-76.
- Pierce RH, Kirkpatrick GJ. Innovative techniques for harmful algal toxin analysis. *Environ Toxicol Chem* 2001;20:107-14.
- Pistocchi R, Pezzolesi L, Guerrini F, Vanucci S, Dell'Aversano C, Fattorusso E. A review on the effects of environmental conditions on growth and toxin production of *Ostreopsis ovata*. *Toxicon* 2011;57:421-8.
- Plumley FG. Marine algal toxins: Biochemistry, genetics, and molecular biology. *Limnol Oceanogr* 1997;42:1252-64.

- Pollinger U, Zemel E. In situ and experimental evidence of the influence of turbulence on cell division processes of *Peridinium cinctum* forma *westii* (Lemm.) Lefevre. *Brit Phycol J* 1981;16:281-7.
- Quilliam MA. Chemical methods for lipophilic shellfish toxins. In: Hallegraeff GM, Anderson DM, Cembella AD, editors. *Manual on harmful marine microalgae*. Paris: UNESCO Publishing; 2003. p. 211-245.
- Ramaswamy AV. Cloning and biochemical characterization of the hectochlorin biosynthetic gene cluster from the marine cyanobacterium *Lyngbya majuscula*. *J Nat Prod* 2007;70:1977-86.
- Redden JM, Dodge-Kafka KL. AKAP phosphatase complexes in the heart. *J Cardiovasc Pharm* 2011;58:354-62.
- Rein KS, Borrone J. Polyketides from dinoflagellates: Origins, pharmacology and biosynthesis. *Comp Biochem Phys B* 1999;124:117-31.
- Rein KS, Snyder RV. The biosynthesis of polyketide metabolites by dinoflagellates. *Adv Appl Microbiol* 2006;59:93-125.
- Roenneberg T, Merrow M. "What watch?... such much!" Complexity and evolution of circadian clocks. *Cell Tissue Res* 2002;309:3-9.
- Rublee PA, Kempton JW, Schaefer EF, Allen C, Harris J, Oldach DW, Bowers H, Tengs T, Burkholder JM, Glasgow HB. Use of molecular probes to assess geographic distribution of *Pfiesteria* species. *Environ Health Persp* 2001;109:765-7.
- Rublee PA, Remington DL, Schaefer EF, Marshall MM. Detection of the dinozoans *Pfiesteria piscicida* and *P. shumwayae*: A review of detection methods and geographic distribution. *J Eukaryot Microbiol* 2005;52:83-9.

- Salomon CE, Magarvey NA, Sherman DH. Merging the potential of microbial genetics with biological and chemical diversity: An even brighter future for marine natural product drug discovery. *Nat Prod Rep* 2004;21:105-21.
- Samdal IA, Aasen JAB, Briggs LR, Dahl E, Miles CO. Comparison of ELISA and LC-MS analyses for yessotoxins in blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*). *Toxicon* 2005;46:7-15.
- Sánchez Pérez JA, Rodríguez Porcel EM, Casas López JL, Fernández Sevilla JM, Chisti Y. Shear rate in stirred tank and bubble column bioreactors. *Chem Eng J* 2006;124:1-5.
- Satoh M, Koshino H, Nakata T. Synthetic studies on maitotoxin. 3. Stereoselective synthesis of the BCDE-ring system. *Org Lett* 2008;10:1683-5.
- Scatasta S, Stoltel W, Granéli E, Weikard HP, van Ierland E. Harmful algal blooms in European marine waters: Socio-economic analysis of selected case studies. Contract EVK3-CT-2001-80003. Wageningen University, the Netherlands, and Kalmar University, Sweden; 2003.
- Schofield O, Grzymiski J, Bissett WP, Kirkpatrick GJ, Millie DF, Moline M, Roesler CS. Optical monitoring and forecasting systems for harmful algal blooms: Possibility or pipe dream? *J Phycol* 1999;35:1477-96.
- Scholin CA, Anderson DM. Detection and quantification of HAB species using antibody and DNA probes: Progress to date and future research objectives. In: Reguera B, Blanco J, Fernández ML, Wyatt T, editors. Harmful algae. Santiago de Compostela, Spain: Xunta de Galicia and Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO; 1998. p. 253-257.
- Scorzetti G. Multiple simultaneous detection of harmful algal blooms (HABs) through a high throughput bead array technology, with potential use in phytoplankton community analysis. *Harmful Algae* 2009;8:196-211.

- Sekida S, Takahira M, Horiguchi T, Okuda K. Effects of high pressure in the armored dinoflagellate *Scrippsiella hexapraeicingula* (Peridinales, Dinophyceae): changes in thecal plate pattern and microtubule assembly. *J Phycol* 2012;48:163-73.
- Selander E, Pavia H. Method to enhance production of paralytic shellfish toxins from dinoflagellate cultures. US Patent Application 2009291484; 2009.
- Sellner KG, Doucette GJ, Kirkpatrick GJ. Harmful algal blooms: Causes, impacts and detection. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol* 2003;30:383-406.
- Shimizu Y. Microalgal metabolites: A new perspective. *Annu Rev Microbiol* 1996;50:431-65.
- Shimizu Y. Microalgae as a drug source. In: Fusetani N, editor. *Drugs from the sea*. Basel: Karger; 2000. p. 30-45.
- Shimizu Y. Microalgal metabolites. *Curr Opin Microbiol* 2003;6:236-43.
- Singh S, Kate BN, Banerjee UC. Bioactive compounds from cyanobacteria and microalgae: An overview. *Crit Rev Biotechnol* 2005;25:73-95.
- Skelton HM. Axenic culture of the heterotrophic dinoflagellate *Pfiesteria shumwayae* in a semi-defined medium. *J Eukaryot Microbiol* 2009;56:73-82.
- Snyder RV, Gibbs PDL, Palacios A, Abiy L, Dickey R, Lopez JV, Rein KS. Polyketide synthase genes from marine dinoflagellates. *Mar Biotechnol* 2003;5:1-12.
- Stoecker DK, Long A, Suttles SE, Sanford LP. Effect of small-scale shear on grazing and growth of the dinoflagellate *Pfiesteria piscicida*. *Harmful Algae* 2006;5:407-18.
- Suzuki C, Nakajima Y, Akimoto H, Wu C, Ohmiya Y. A new additional reporter enzyme, dinoflagellate luciferase, for monitoring of gene expression in mammalian cells. *Gene* 2005;344:61-6.
- Sullivan JM, Swift E. Effects of small-scale turbulence on net growth rate and size of ten species of marine dinoflagellates. *J Phycol* 2003;39:83-94.

- Sullivan JM, Swift E, Donaghay PL, Rines JEB. Small-scale turbulence affects the division rate and morphology of two red-tide dinoflagellates. *Harmful Algae* 2003;2:183-99.
- Suresh S, Srivastava VC, Mishra IM. Critical analysis of engineering aspects of shaken flask bioreactors Analysis of shaken flask bioreactors. *Crit Rev Biotechnol* 2009;29:255-78.
- Tang EPY. Why do dinoflagellates have lower growth rates? *J Phycol* 1996;32:80-4.
- Tang JQ, Li T, Yang WD, Liu JS, Li HY. Cloning and analysis of PKS gene from *Prorocentrum lima*. *Shengtai Xuebao/Acta Ecologica Sinica* 2009;29:2383-90.
- Taroncher-Oldenburg G. Toxin availability during the cell cycle of the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium fundyense*. *Limnol Oceanogr* 1998;42:1178-88.
- Taroncher-Oldenburg C, Anderson DM. Identification and characterization of three differentially expressed genes, encoding S-adenosylhomocysteine hydrolase, methionine aminopeptidase, and a histone-like protein, in the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium fundyense*. *Appl Environ Microb* 2000;66:2105-12.
- Taylor FJR. General group characteristics; special features of interest; short history of dinoflagellate study. In: Taylor FJR, editor. *The biology of dinoflagellates*. New York: Wiley; 1987. p. 1-23.
- Taylor FJR, Fukuyo Y, Larsen J, Hallegraeff GM. Taxonomy of harmful dinoflagellates. In: Hallegraeff GM, Anderson DM, Cembella AD, editors. *Manual on harmful marine microalgae*. Paris: UNESCO Publishing; 2003. p. 389-432.
- ten Lohuis MR, Miller DJ. Genetic transformation of dinoflagellates (*Amphidinium* and *Symbiodinium*): Expression of GUS in microalgae using heterologous promoter constructs. *Plant J* 1998;13:427-35.
- Tester PA, Shea D, Kibler SR, Varnam SM, Black MD, Litaker RW. Relationships among water column toxins, cell abundance and chlorophyll concentrations during *Karenia brevis* blooms. *Cont Shelf Res* 2008;28:59-72.

- Thomas WH, Gibson CH. Quantified small-scale turbulence inhibits a red tide dinoflagellate, *Gonyaulax polyedra* Stein. Deep-Sea Res 1990;37:1583-93.
- Thomas WH, Gibson CH. Effects of quantified small-scale turbulence on the dinoflagellate, *Gymnodium sanguineum* (Splendens): contrasts with *Gonyaulax* (*Lingulodinium*) *polyedra*, and the fishery implication. Deep-Sea Res 1992;39:1429-37.
- Thomas WH, Vernet M, Gibson CH. Effects of small-scale turbulence on photosynthesis, pigmentation, cell division, and cell size in the marine dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax polyedra* (Dinophyceae). J Phycol 1995;31:50-9.
- Tsukano C, Ebine M, Sasaki M. Convergent total synthesis of gymnocin-A and evaluation of synthetic analogues. J Am Chem Soc 2005;127:4326-35.
- Tyrrell JV, Bergquist PR, Saul DJ, MacKenzie L, Bergquist PL. Oligonucleotide probe technology as applied to the study of harmful algal blooms. New Zeal J Mar Fresh 1997;31:551-60.
- Tynan CT. The effects of small scale turbulence on dino-flagellates. PhD dissertation, University of California at San Diego, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, California; 1993.
- Varley J, Birch J. Reactor design for large scale suspension animal cell culture. Cytotechnol 1999;29:177-205.
- Veldhuis MJW, Cucci TL, Sieracki ME. Cellular DNA content of marine phytoplankton using two new fluorochromes: Taxonomic and ecological implications. J Phycol 1997;33:527-41.
- Wang D-Z. Neurotoxins from marine dinoflagellates: A brief review. Mar Drugs 2008;6:349-71.

- Wang C, Hsieh DDP. Nutritional supplementation to increase growth and paralytic shellfish toxin productivity by the marine dinoflagellate *Alexandrium tamarense*. *Biochem Eng J* 2002;11:131-5.
- Wang DZ, Ho AYT, Hsieh DPH. Production of C2 toxin by *Alexandrium tamarense* CI01 using different culture methods. *J Appl Phycol* 2002;14:461-8.
- Wang L, Sang Y-X, Wang X-H. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay for okadaic acid: Investigation of analytical conditions and sample matrix on assay performance. *J AOAC Int* 2011;94:1531-9.
- Wang Q, Liu Y-C, Li J, Jiang W, Chen Y-J, Song N-N. Development of a chemiluminescent ELISA for determining okadaic acid in shellfish. *J Food Quality* 2012;35:76-82.
- Weuster-Botz D. Experimental design for fermentation media development: Statistical design or global random search? *J Biosci Bioeng* 2000;90:473-83.
- White AW. Growth inhibition caused by turbulence in the toxic marine dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax excavata*. *J Fish Res Board Can* 1976;33:2598-602.
- Wisecaver JH, Hackett JD. Dinoflagellate genome evolution. *Annu Rev Microbiol* 2011;65:369-87.
- Wong JTY, Kwok ACM. Proliferation of dinoflagellates: Blooming or bleaching. *BioEssays* 2005;27:730-40.
- Wong TYJ, Yeung KK, Wong TWF. Method for the production of dinoflagellate cultures. US Patent 7,396,672; 2008.
- Wong C-K, Hung P, Ng EAL, Lee KLH, Wong GTC, Kam K-M. Operational application of a rapid antibody-based detection assay for first line screening of paralytic shellfish toxins in shellfish. *Harmful Algae* 2010;9:636-46.

- Wright JLC. Biosynthesis of DTX-4: Confirmation of a polyketide pathway, proof of a Baeyer–Villiger oxidation step, and evidence for an unusual carbon deletion process. *J Am Chem Soc* 1996;118:8757-8.
- Wurm FM. Production of recombinant protein therapeutics in cultivated mammalian cells. *Nat Biotechnol* 2004;22:1393-8.
- Xu QH, Wei CH, Huang K, Rong KT. Toxin-neutralizing effect and activity-quality relationship for mice tetrodotoxin-specific polyclonal antibodies. *Toxicology* 2005a;206:439-48.
- Xu QH, Zhao XN, Wei CH, Rong KT. Immunologic protection of anti-tetrodotoxin vaccines against lethal activities of oral tetrodotoxin challenge in mice. *Int Immunopharmacol* 2005b;5:1213-24.
- Yeung PKK. Inhibition of cell proliferation by mechanical agitation involves transient cell cycle arrest at G1 phase in dinoflagellates. *Protoplasma* 2003;220:173-8.
- Yeung PKK. Involvement of calcium mobilization from caffeine-sensitive stores in mechanically induced cell cycle arrest in the dinoflagellate *Cryptocodinium cohnii*. *Cell Calcium* 2006;39:259-74.
- Yeung PKK, Wong JTY. Inhibition of cell proliferation by mechanical agitation involves transient cell cycle arrest at G1 phase in dinoflagellates. *Protoplasma* 2003;220:173-8.
- Zirbel MJ, Veron F, Latz MI. The reversible effect of flow on the morphology of *Ceratocorys horrida* (Peridinales, Dinophyta). *J Phycol* 2000;36:46-58.

Table 1. Prices (€·mg⁻¹ in 2011) of dinoflagellates toxins

Biotoxin	Source								
	SGA	ALEX	LKT	VWR	WK ^a	LD	GEN ^b	SL	PKC
Okadaic acid, sodium salt	6760	1694	3774	4490	-	3254	5110	2690	872
Okadaic acid, potassium salt	5560	1694	-	-	-	3560	-	5970	872
Okadaic acid (HPLC film)	6280	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Okadaic acid	901	1880	3432	4870	2040	3865	3010	3486	872
Okadaic acid, ammonium salt	9460	1694	3774	-	1360	3650	5110	-	872
Okadaic acid (chemical synthesis) ^c	340	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Okadaol	7400	-	-	-	-	4228	10380	8918	-
Saxitoxin, diacetate	13450	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Neo-saxitoxin	30980	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Brevetoxin 2	10500	-	-	-	-	-	8754	-	-
Brevetoxin 3	-	-	-	-	-	-	8526	-	-
Brevetoxin 6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Brevetoxin 9	13800	-	-	-	-	-	9464	-	-
Palytoxin	-	-	-	-	3600	-	-	-	-
Maitotoxin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dinophysistoxin-1	-	-	-	-	2040	-	-	-	-
Dinophysistoxin-4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tetrodotoxin	-	-	-	-	-	-	276	-	-

SGA: Sigma-Aldrich (www.sigmaaldrich.com); GEN: Gentaur Molecular Products (www.gentaur.com); LD: The Lab Depot (www.labdepotinc.com); SL: ScienceLab (www.sciencelab.com); PKC: PKC Pharmaceuticals Inc. (www.lclabs.com); TK: Tocris (www.tocris.com); WK: Wako Pure Chemical Industries Ltd (www.wako-chem.com); ALEX: Alexis (www.alexis-corp.com); VWR: VWR International (www.vwrsp.com). ^a Wako produces okadaic acid from the marine sponge *Halichondria okadai*. ^b Tetrodotoxin from bacterial cultures. ^c Production discontinued.

Table 2. Energy dissipation rate (ε) damage threshold for dinoflagellates

No.	Order	Organism	Inhibitory ε ($\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$)	Reference
1	Gonyaulacales	<i>Lingulodinium polyedrum</i>	0.045	Thomas et al. (1995)
2	Gonyaulacales	<i>Alexandrium fundyense</i>	0.1	Juhl et al. (2001)
3	Gonyaulacales	<i>Ceratocorys horrida</i>	0.1	Zirbel et al. (2000)
4	Gonyaulacales	<i>Crypthecodinium cohnii</i>	0.1	Yeung and Wong (2003)
5	Gonyaulacales	<i>L. polyedrum</i>	0.15	Thomas and Gibson (1990)
6	Gonyaulacales	<i>L. polyedrum</i>	0.18	Juhl et al. (2000)
7	Gonyaulacales	<i>L. polyedrum</i>	0.2	Juhl and Latz (2002)
8	Gonyaulacales	<i>L. polyedrum</i>	0.2	Thomas and Gibson (1990)
9	Gonyaulacales	<i>L. polyedrum</i>	0.73	Gibson and Thomas (1995)
10	Gonyaulacales	<i>Protoceratium reticulatum</i>	0.8	García Camacho et al. (2007b)
11	Gonyaulacales	<i>A. fundyense</i>	1	Sullivan and Swift (2003)
12	Gonyaulacales	<i>Ceratium fusus</i>	1	Sullivan and Swift (2003)
13	Gonyaulacales	<i>Ceratium tripos</i>	1	Sullivan and Swift (2003)
14	Gonyaulacales	<i>C. tripos</i>	1	Sullivan and Swift (2003)
15	Gonyaulacales	<i>C. tripos</i>	1	Havskum et al. (2005)
16	Gonyaulacales	<i>Oxyrrhis marina</i>	1	Havskum (2003)
17	Gonyaulacales	<i>Pyrocystis noctiluca</i>	1	Sullivan and Swift (2003)
18	Gonyaulacales	<i>L. polyedrum</i>	3.5	Juhl and Latz (2002)
19	Gonyaulacales	<i>L. polyedrum</i>	10	Sullivan et al. (2003)
20	Gymnodiniales	<i>Akashiwo sanguinea</i>	0.011	Thomas and Gibson (1992)
21	Gymnodiniales	<i>A. sanguinea</i>	1	Berdalet (1992)
22	Gymnodiniales	<i>A. sanguinea</i>	2	Berdalet (1992)
23	Gymnodiniales	<i>A. sanguinea</i>	4.6	Tynan (1993)

No.	Order	Organism	Inhibitory ε ($\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-3}$)	Reference
24	Peridinales	<i>Heterocapsa triquetra</i>	0.1	Dempsey (1982)
25	Peridinales	<i>H. triquetra</i>	0.1	Yeung and Wong (2003)
26	Peridinales	<i>Scrippsiella trochoidea</i>	2	Berdalet and Estrada (1993)
27	Prorocentrales	<i>Prorocentrum micans</i>	2	Berdalet and Estrada (1993)
28	Prorocentrales	<i>Prorocentrum triestinum</i>	2	Berdalet and Estrada (1993)

Figure 1. Specific energy dissipation rates (ϵ) required to inhibit growth of dinoflagellates. The numbers next to the data refer to the species in Table 2. Dashed lines demarcate the ranges of ϵ values encountered in common industrial bubble column and stirred tank types of bioreactors and typical animal cell bioreactors.